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On- and off-axis tension-compression and self-heating behavior of a woven CFRP up to the very high cycle fatigue regime

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Department of Sustainable Systems Engineering (INATECH)

Walter-and-Ingeborg-Herrmann-Chair for Power Ultrasonics and Engineering of Functional Materials (EFM)

University of Freiburg (Germany)

ICCM- 24th International Conference on Composite Materials

Baltimore, USA

04th – 08th August 2025

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Schematic of ultrasonic fatigue test system for polymer composites

Premanand and Balle (2023),
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultras.2023.107130>

Different types of ultrasonic boosters

Premanand, Schimmelpfeng and Balle (2025),
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2025.112183>

Setting up 3D-Laservibrometry on axial loading system – Physical setup

Ultrasonic pulse and pause signals captured with the single-point LDV

3D- Scanning laser Doppler vibrometer

Premanand and Balle (2023),
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultras.2023.107130>

Preliminary design of CF -PEKKspecimen oscillation due at 20 kHz

Specimen geometry dimensions in mm

Ansys harmonic analysis

Measurement of oscillations using 3D SLV

Exemplary strain distribution during ultrasonic loading

Premanand and Balle (2023),
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultras.2023.107130>

Specimen and experiment **design requirements**

- How to have a **universal geometry** for low frequency and ultrasonic frequency fatigue experiments?

Modal analysis

- How are the **achievable stress levels** for low frequency and ultrasonic frequency fatigue experiments?

Harmonic analysis

- How to **avoid buckling** of composites during low frequency fatigue under R=-1 ratio?

Buckling analysis

- What would be the **optimal pulse -pause sequence** ?

- How does **the surface temperature** compare to servo-hydraulic testing?

**Self-heating analysis
Increasing amplitude fatigue
(IAF) experiments**

- How are the fatigue lives affected under different testing condition

Constant amplitude fatigue (CAF) experiments

Modal analysis: Stiffness as function of fiber orientation

Stiffness properties of rotated laminate

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_x}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & \frac{\nu_{xy}E_y}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{xy}E_y}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & \frac{E_y}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{xy} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$Q_\theta = T^T Q T$$

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2(\theta) & \sin^2(\theta) & 2\cos(\theta)\sin(\theta) \\ \sin^2(\theta) & \cos^2(\theta) & -2\cos(\theta)\sin(\theta) \\ -\cos(\theta)\sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta)\sin(\theta) & \cos^2(\theta) - \sin^2(\theta) \end{bmatrix}$$

Specimen geometries for on - and off -axis loading

Premanand, Schimmelpfeng and Balle (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2025.112183>

Harmonic analysis: Normal stresses during ultrasonic fatigue

- Stresses at the edges higher than in the bulk (a and b).
- Stress concentration (highest for 0°) decreases with increasing off-axis orientation
- Maximum stresses must be used instead of nominal stress for fatigue analysis

Premanand, Schimmelpfeng and Balle (2025),
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2025.112183>

Buckling analysis: Strength as a function of fiber orientation

Theoretical strength values of the composite laminate as a function of laminate orientation (off-axis angle) with loading direction

Side and front view schematic of the dogbone-shaped CF-PEKK specimen under compression in a SH fatigue system for buckling analysis

Buckling mode determined using eigenvalue buckling analysis and finite element modeling (FEM)

Tsai- Hill static failure criterion

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_x}{X}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{\sigma_x \sigma_y}{XY}\right) + \left(\frac{\sigma_y}{Y}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{xy}}{S}\right)^2 = 1$$

$$P_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 E I_{avg}}{L_{gauge}^2}$$

Off -axis angles θ [°]	Maximum compressive load P_c [kN]	Gage length L_{gage} [mm]	Critical buckling length L_{cr} [mm]	Critical buckling load P_{cr} [kN]
0	8.6	52	50.2	15
15	7.1	50	55.1	15.4
30	5.5	42	56.6	17
45	5.0	36	55.2	19.4

Temperature response for low-frequency fatigue

Temperature response for ultrasonic-frequency fatigue

- Temperature plays major role in off-axis orientation
- Frequency of 20 Hz applicable for LFFT

- Temperature increases with increasing off axis angle
- 50ms/3s has no undesirable temperature effect

Premanand, Schimmelpfeng and Balle (2025),
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2025.112183>

f = 20 Hz

f = 20,000 Hz

Comparable self-heating surface temperature distribution at 20 Hz and 20,000 Hz !

Experimental results: CAF experiments @ SH and UFT

- ◻ 0°, 20 Hz failure
- ◻ 15°, 20 Hz failure
- ◻ 30°, 20 Hz failure
- ◻ 45°, 20 Hz failure
- ◻ 0°, 20 kHz failure
- ◻ 15°, 20 kHz failure
- ◻ 30°, 20 kHz failure
- ◻ 45°, 20 kHz failure
- ◻ 0°, 20 Hz run-out
- ◻ 15°, 20 Hz run-out
- ◻ 30°, 20 Hz run-out
- ◻ 45°, 20 Hz run-out
- ◻ 0°, 20 kHz run-out
- ◻ 15°, 20 kHz run-out
- ◻ 30°, 20 kHz run-out
- ◻ 45°, 20 kHz run-out

- Similar stress levels:
- ❖ similar incident of damage initiation
 - ❖ slower accumulation rate under ultrasonic fatigue testing

Conclusions

➤ **Specimen design for on - and off -axis fatigue loading up to very high cycle fatigue regime must include:**

- Harmonic analysis to calculate the stresses due to resonance at 20 kHz
- Buckling analysis for reversed uni-axial loading conditions
- Structural analysis to determine the stress concentration in a curved (dog-bone shaped) specimen

➤ **The self -heating behavior of CF -PEKK specimens at 20 Hz and 20 kHz:**

Temperature does not significantly influence the fatigue life of the off-axis specimens due to the difference in test frequencies, provided that thermo-mechanical effects are avoided.

➤ **Damage initiation location for dog -bone shaped CF -PEKK specimens:**

The VHCF damage in woven composites initiates at the surface under uni-axial loading.

- ❖ Due to free edge effect
- ❖ Stress concentration
- ❖ Multiaxial stresses

Related publications and further reading

Development of an axial loading system for fatigue testing of textile-composites at ultrasonic frequencies

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
CFRP
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20 kHz

ABSTRACT

Fiber-reinforced polymers are increasingly used in lightweight applications due to their high specific properties. Different polymer materials, and fiber architectures, are commercially available for structural applications. Performing fatigue experiments on all these combinations of fiber-matrix composites up to 10^9 cycles to mimic their typical lifetime of 15–20 years, at a low testing frequency generally in the range of 5–10 Hz in applications such as the aerospace industry, is expensive and time-consuming. In this study, a test system to investigate the very high cycle fatigue (VHCF) behavior of continuous fiber-reinforced polymers under an axial loading (tension-compression) condition is proposed. To do so, a testing system capable of applying cyclic oscillations at a frequency of 20 kHz and stress ratio, $R = -1$ was developed. For this investigation, the carbon fiber reinforced in Polyether-ketone-ketone (CF-PEKK) material was chosen. For visualization of the specimen oscillation-mode at 20 kHz, video-imaging using a high-speed camera (HSC) was employed. With the obtained displacement field from the HSC images and with thermography, the desired specimen response due to resonance at 20 kHz is validated.

Premanand and Balle (2022),
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mlblux.2022.100131>

Stress and strain calculation method for orthotropic polymer composites under axial and bending ultrasonic fatigue loads

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Ultrasonic fatigue testing
Carbon fiber reinforced polymers
Laser Doppler vibrometry
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Harmonic analysis

ABSTRACT

Accelerated fatigue testing is one potential solution to evaluate the very high cycle fatigue behavior of composite materials within a reasonable amount of time. The ultrasonic fatigue testing methodology can be adopted to realize fatigue experiments up to 10^9 cycles at 20 kHz, compared to conventional fatigue experiments usually carried out between 5–50 Hz. The determination of cyclic stresses during ultrasonic loading remains to be one of the major challenges. The cyclic stresses during ultrasonic fatigue loading were investigated for a carbon fiber 5H satin fabric reinforced in Polyetherketoneketone (CF-PEKK) composite material. Two experimental setups were developed to perform ultrasonic testing under uni-axial and three-point bending loading conditions. A 3D-Scanning Laser Doppler Vibrometer (3D-SLDV) and a single-point Laser Doppler Vibrometer (LDV) were integrated into the test systems to measure the oscillation displacement of the CF-PEKK specimens during ultrasonic cyclic loading. These displacement measurements were used to calculate the resulting strains and stresses under elastic loading conditions. The experimental results were found to be in good agreement with those obtained from finite element models, providing evidence for applying the proposed method.

Premanand and Balle (2023),
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultras.2023.107130>

Specimen and experiment design for on- and off-axis fatigue and self-heating characterization of a woven CF-PEKK composite at low and ultrasonic frequencies

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Ultrasonic fatigue testing
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Very high cycle fatigue
Uni-axial loading
Off-axis testing

ABSTRACT

This work investigates the fatigue behavior of satin fabric-woven carbon fiber-reinforced poly-ether-ketone (PEKK) laminates under low (20 Hz) and ultrasonic (20 kHz) testing frequencies using identical specimen geometries. Specimen designs across all orientations were based on modal, harmonic, static-structural, and buckling analyses to ensure comparable results. This design enables uniaxial tension-compression loading of woven carbon-fiber reinforced polymers (CFRPs) to fail in the gauge section without global buckling and ensures overlapping stress amplitudes between the two test systems. The maximum possible stress amplitudes of ultrasonic fatigue testing (UFT) are higher than the lowest stress amplitudes that cause failure in the conventional servo-hydraulic (SH) system. By using the anisotropy of composite laminates, this design was validated through tension-compression experiments on dogbone-shaped specimens with four fiber orientations: 0°, 15°, 30°, and 45°, using SH and UFT systems. Results comparing high-cycle fatigue (HCF) and very high-cycle fatigue (VHCF) behavior of angle-ply laminates indicate a strong dependence on fiber orientation. A comparison of self-heating and microscopic analysis between the two systems demonstrates the applicability of UFT for off-axis VHCF characterization of woven composites. Finally, shear stress-induced damage initiation in 0° fiber-oriented dog-bone-shaped specimens, as observed in this work and reported in the literature, is addressed as a multi-axial stress state problem by incorporating the resultant normal, transverse, and shear stresses into the Tsai-Wu formulation.

Premanand, Schimmelpfeng and Balle (2025),
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2025.112183>

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